

| Research Article

The Diminishing Family Relationship and Societal Transition in R. K. Narayan's the Vendor of Sweets

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Abstract: “The Vendor of Sweets” deals with the clash between traditional and Western cultures, the complex father-son relationship marked by communication failures and generational divides, the struggle with wealth and materialism versus spiritual ideals, and a quest for identity and self-renewal in a changing post-colonial India. Narayan’s novel explores the loss of traditional values and cultural identity that can accompany rapid modernization, as India grapples with the legacies of British colonialism and the influence of U.S.-dominated global culture.

Keywords: Transition, Family, relationship, tradition, Indian life, colonial

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“The zone where the natives live is not complementary to the zone inhabited by the settlers. The two zones are opposed, but not in the service of a higher unity. Obedient to the rules of pure Aristotelian logic, they follow the principles of mutual exclusivity. No conciliation is possible....”

Frantz Fanon, *The Wretched Earth*

Frantz Fanon's work, describes the spatial and social segregation enforced by colonialism, where the spaces inhabited by the indigenous population ("natives") are kept separate and distinct from the areas occupied by the colonizers, with no possibility of meaningful interaction or integration between the two groups; essentially highlighting the inherent conflict and division created by colonial power dynamics. He tries to analyze the psychological and social effects of colonialism on the indigenous population, emphasizing the power dynamics of oppression and resistance.

Narayan’s novel explores the loss of traditional values and cultural identity that can accompany rapid modernization, as India grapples with the legacies of British colonialism and the influence of U.S.-dominated global culture. Narayan in his novel “The Vendor of Sweets” uses the generational conflict between the protagonist, Jagan, and his son, Mali, as the central theme. Jagan embodies a conflicted traditionalism, aspiring to Gandhian asceticism while clinging to materialism, while Mali represents a restless, uncritical modernity, characterized by Western ideals and a pursuit of material success. The diminishing family relationship is a microcosm of a society in transition, where a fundamental breakdown in communication and a chasm of values are symptoms of larger societal changes. Narayan also uses the novel to critique how post-independence society was corrupted by both former colonial attitudes and the rise of Western-

dominated global capitalism. Mali's business venture represents the negative side of globalization, which seeks to manipulate and exploit indigenous culture for financial gain

Most of R.K Narayan's novels is an anecdote of life in Southern India and a study of conventions, traditions, manners, beliefs, and superstitions. Narayan's novels make a minute study on adult psychology in Indian scenario. They are studies of mind and behavior of adult people. They deal with themes related to physical, intellectual, emotional social, moral and volitional aspect of human behavior. His novels develops characters, particularly their interactions and their quest for dharma, exploring the subtle complexities of human nature and traditional Indian life. Narayan's works are analyzed for their keen observation and depiction of Indian socio-cultural traditions, including marriage, family dynamics, and the impact of modern life on traditional values.

In *Black Skin White Masks* , Frantz Fanon articulates the need of a different history that is not written by the colonizers:

“ ...But I too can recover my past, and give it a value or blame it for my subsequent choices....If a white man disputes my human nature, I will show him, by making his life bear all my manly weight, that I am not the Y a bon banania that he still imagines....I am not History's prisoner....It is by overcoming what has been historically given, the instrumental, that I start the cycle of my freedom.”

(In *Black Skin White Masks*)

One finds Narayan expressing the need of resisting the British version of Indian history and creating a purified Indian history in his handling of the historical Association. Colonial rule, which was hegemonic, depended heavily on the ability to hide from native Indians true historical facts, and also on the ability to distort historical events to suit their purposes.

Narayan's novels make a minute study on adult psychology in Indian scenario. They are studies of mind and behavior of adult people. They deal with themes related to physical, intellectual, emotional social, moral and volitional aspect of human behavior. His novels develops characters, particularly their interactions and their quest for dharma, exploring the subtle complexities of human nature and traditional Indian life. Narayan's works are analyzed for their keen observation and depiction of Indian socio-cultural traditions, including marriage, family dynamics, and the impact of modern life on traditional values. It will be important to quote Ania Loomba,

“Historically speaking anti-colonial resistances have taken many forms, and they have drawn upon a wide variety of resources.... Anticolonial struggles therefore had to create new and powerful identities for colonized peoples and to challenge colonialism not only at a political or intellectual level, but also on an emotional plane....”

(Colonialism/Post Colonialism)

“The Vendor of Sweets” deals with the clash between traditional and Western cultures, the complex father-son relationship marked by communication failures and generational divides, the struggle with wealth and materialism versus spiritual ideals, and a quest for identity and self-renewal in a changing post-colonial India. It offers us a comprehensive view of life of a vendor who serves as a peg on which the novel treats life imaginatively and holds a mirror of stark reality of Jagan's family. On one side we have the stark reality of poverty-stricken life of vagrant Jagan and on the other side the sinful life of his son Mali.

Jagan is 55 years old at the beginning of the novel and lives a life of strict asceticism, eating only wheat, greens, and honey, even cutting salt and sugar from his diet. He closely follows the Bhagavad Gita (or simply, the Gita), a core Hindu scripture that Gandhi referred to as his “spiritual dictionary.” Formerly politically active, and in fact jailed for demonstrating during India's revolution, he now lives a quiet life as a widower and successful businessman. He believes

strongly in naturopathy, and has in fact written a book on the subject, the publication of which is long-delayed by the printer. Jagan's wife, Ambika, died many years ago due to his insistence on treating her with natural remedies. Though he practices personal asceticism, he makes his living indulging others' desire for sweets, and showcases greed by squirreling away a portion of his profits before taxation.

R.K. Narayan's *The Vendor of Sweets* uses the fractured relationship between the Gandhian father, Jagan, and his Westernized son, Mali, to illustrate the erosion of family ties due to generational conflict and the clash between traditional values and modern influences. The story acts as an anecdote for diminishing family relationships by showing how Mali's materialistic aspirations and abandonment of traditional education create a vast gap between him and his father, ultimately leading to a significant breakdown in their familial bond.

The novel depicts the many-sided aspects of life and society, variously different and even opposite to each other. It is preoccupied with subjects like love, sex, money, family life, conflicts, tensions, order and disorder, the good and the evil, and the east-west tension. The other sub themes that the novel explores are the generation gap, the role of Gandhi in society, the Hindu way of life, and the Indianness of India.

Narayan's novel is imbued with tradition and values embedded in Indian society. It depicts the Joint family fabric of South India. 'Vendor of Sweets' is of no exception. It depicts Joint family of Jagan's parents. The detailed description of Jagan's ancestral joint family through analepsis and prolepsis is noteworthy. We do see that Jagan in his old age sighs for the warm and crowded days of his parents. There was a time when all the rooms of the big house dazzled with light. There was noise and bustle in the crowded house. Gradually, family members moved out of the house and slowly the crowded joint family which once bustled with animation and noise became calm and lonely, leaving only Jagan and Mali.

Ruined by Jagan's excessive pampering love and affection, Mali is a ruined child. He returns to Malgudi with 'other person' Grace, half Korean and half American Girl, whom he introduces as his wife. Jagan feels affronted, and when he learns that Mali and Grace are not married, he feels tantalized. He thinks that his house is polluted and he barricades himself in his part of the house and uses a back door for coming and going. Jagan is confused with a shocking world in which his notions of marriage and morals are shattered. The story highlights the clash between old and new generations, with the death of the mother acting as a catalyst for the family's disintegration and the deepening emotional distance between Jagan and Mali. The introduction of Mali's American wife, Grace, further complicates the traditional family structure, showcasing the impact of cultural change on familial bonds.

Here Bhabha's definition of culture comes to fore. Homi K. Bhabha views culture not as a fixed entity but as a dynamic and negotiated space of "cultural difference" found in the "in-between" or "interstitial" areas where different cultural traditions interact. He emphasizes cultural hybridity, where elements from the colonizer and colonized interweave to create new hybrid identities that challenge essentialist views of culture.

Indian writers, particularly in the early and mid-20th century, used fiction to assert cultural identity amidst colonial influence. Narayan was not exception to this. He uses the his fiction as tools for cultural preservation, capturing traditions, festivals, beliefs, and rituals that define Indian society.. He depicts everyday life in a manner that celebrates Indian values while subtly addressing change and continuity. Cultural Studies, examines how literature reflects, constructs and negotiates cultural identities. It considers literature as a site of cultural meaning-making, which is central to analyzing Narayan's representation of Indian traditions, family structures, religious practices, and social hierarchies. In "The Vendor of Sweets", Jagan's entrepreneurial zeal and business correspondence in English coexist with his adherence to devotional practices

and family-centric values. Narayan portrays Indian responses to Western influence as selective and adaptive: rather than wholesale Westernization.

Conclusion:

As Postcolonial theorist like Edward Said, Homi Bhabha, and Gayatri Spivak, articulates the Indian scenario painted by R K Narayan provides ample space for evaluation of decaying social and cultural space when confronted by colonial venture. The Postcolonial theorists explores fiction as a fertile ground to explore themes such as colonial influence, hybridity, identity, and resistance in Narayan’s fiction. Though Narayan does not confront colonialism directly, his subtle critique of Westernization and his affirmation of Indian ways of life can be understood through postcolonial paradigms. His works often depict the negotiation between tradition and modernity—a central concern in postcolonial literature.